

CONDUCTIVE NANOCOMPOSITES MANUFACTURED VIA FRONTAL POLYMERIZATION

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ABSTRACT

Frontal polymerization (FP) is a rapid, energy-efficient alternative to conventional manufacturing techniques for polymers and polymer composites. FP has been demonstrated for several polymerization reactions. One of the most promising is the frontal ring-opening metathesis polymerization (FROMP) of dicyclopentadiene (DCPD), which produces polydicyclopentadiene (pDCPD), a cross-linked thermoset polymer with excellent thermomechanical properties. Here we report for the first time the manufacturing of pDCPD matrix nanocomposites via FROMP. First, we describe nanocomposites containing low loadings of carbon nanofillers, below the percolation threshold. The ability of these nanofillers to efficiently convert light into heat enables non-contact photo-activation of FROMP. The efficiency of photo-activation increases by 40× with the addition of only 1 wt% carbon nanoparticles to the neat DCPD resin. Next, we describe nanocomposites containing higher loadings of carbon nanofillers, above the percolation threshold. These nanocomposites exhibit electrical conductivity more than 18 orders of magnitude greater than neat pDCPD. At loadings above the percolation threshold, the nanofillers also function as rheological modifiers which enable direct write 3D printing of the resin in tandem with FROMP.

1 INTRODUCTION

Frontal polymerization (FP) is a rapid curing method in which a liquid monomer is converted into a solid polymer via the spatial propagation of a self-sustaining exothermic reaction wave. FP employs the enthalpy of polymerization as the energy source for materials synthesis rather than relying on an external energy source, which offers great promise for energy-efficient manufacturing. The introduction of FP into the manufacturing of thermoset polymers and thermoset matrix composites may save up to ten orders of magnitude in energy and two orders of magnitude in manufacturing time for large parts [1]. FP is a versatile technique, having been applied to several polymerization reactions including acrylate chain growth polymerization [2]–[4], thiol-ene step growth polymerization [5], and epoxy resin curing [6], [7].

Frontal ring-opening metathesis polymerization (FROMP) of dicyclopentadiene (DCPD) has recently garnered attention for its potential use in composite manufacturing [1], [8]–[12]. The FROMP reaction scheme is shown in Figure 1a. The DCPD monomer has a low viscosity, which allows facile processing. The DCPD monomer also has high chemical energy density due to ring strain, which allows FROMP to proceed at relatively fast frontal velocities (Figure 1b), even in the presence of significant volume fractions of inert fillers such as fibers or nanoparticles. Furthermore, the resulting polydicyclopentadiene (pDCPD) product is a cross-linked thermoset polymer with excellent stiffness, strength, fracture toughness, thermal stability, and solvent resistance. In the past, FROMP of DCPD

was limited by short pot life, which is the time at which FP will no longer occur due to decomposition or reaction of reagents. To solve this problem, we recently reported the development of alkyl phosphites as inhibitors which extend the pot life of FROMP resins from less than 1 h to greater than 30 h (Figure 1c), while still allowing FROMP [11].

Figure 1. Alkyl phosphite inhibitors for FROMP. (a) Reaction scheme for the FROMP of DCPD in the presence of a ruthenium (Grubbs) catalyst and a phosphite inhibitor. (b) A sequence of optical images of FROMP propagation through a test tube. (c) The effect of phosphite inhibitors at various concentrations on pot life. FROMP remained possible at all concentrations plotted here [11].

Pot life extension using alkyl phosphite inhibitors opened the door for the manufacturing of composites with microscale continuous fiber reinforcement via FROMP as shown in Figure 2 [1]. However, FROMP has not yet been utilized for the manufacturing of nanocomposites.

Figure 2. Microscale continuous fiber composites manufactured via FROMP. (a) A 900 cm² carbon fiber-reinforced composite panel cured by FROMP in 5 minutes using about 750 J of energy. (b) A corrugated carbon-fiber reinforced composite part. Images from [1].

Nanocomposites have shown promise as multifunctional materials. The reduction in filler size results in a large interfacial area between filler and matrix, which can lead to dramatic property changes even at low filler loadings. For example, the addition of conductive nanofillers can greatly increase the electrical conductivity of the host matrix (typically an insulating polymer) [13]–[15]. Conductive polymer nanocomposites have potential applications in sensing, actuation, electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding, and lightning strike protection [16]. FP is a promising scalable manufacturing technique for nanocomposites because the rapid process limits the time for the nanofillers to agglomerate [17]. Furthermore, the energy and time savings that have been demonstrated for neat polymers and microscale continuous fiber composites should extend to nanocomposites. In the

past, FP has been used to manufacture nanocomposites with various nanofillers including clay, silica, graphene, and carbon nanotubes [17]–[20]. However, very few studies have reported the electrical conductivity of nanocomposites prepared via FP, and those that did showed only modest improvements compared to the neat polymer.

Herein we report the first demonstration of nanocomposite manufacturing via FROMP. First, we describe FROMP-manufactured nanocomposites with low volume fractions of carbon nanoparticles. The photothermal effect exhibited by these nanoparticles [21] enables activation of FROMP with light instead of heat, expanding the versatility of the FROMP manufacturing process. Next, we describe FROMP-manufactured nanocomposites with higher volume fractions of carbon nanoparticles. These nanocomposites can be shaped using direct write 3D printing and exhibit a substantial increase in electrical conductivity compared to neat pDCPD.

2 NANOCOMPOSITES MANUFACTURED VIA PHOTO-ACTIVATED FRONTAL POLYMERIZATION

The FP process consists of activation (i.e. starting the front) and propagation. Most reported FP systems rely upon thermal activation and thermal propagation. Previous reports of FROMP relied upon thermal activation using either a soldering iron or a resistive heater. Activation with light (i.e. photo-activation) instead of heat is an attractive alternative because it enables non-contact, remote activation and may lead to facile multi-point activation in larger systems through appropriate masking.

In this section, we describe photo-activation of FROMP by photothermal heating of carbon nanoparticles including carbon black (CB) and vapor-grown carbon nanofibers (CNF). Despite the morphological differences shown in

Figure 3, both CB and CNF exhibit strong absorption across the UV-visible-near IR spectrum, rendering them the ability of nanoparticles to efficiently convert luminous energy into localized heat. Under proper conditions, the amount of local heat generated by the nanoparticles may be sufficient to activate FROMP.

Figure 3. Scanning electron micrographs of carbon nanoparticles utilized for photo-activation of FROMP showing (a) the spherical, low aspect ratio morphology of CB and (b) the rodlike, high aspect ratio morphology of CNF.

Photothermal heating experiments were performed by irradiating suspensions of carbon nanoparticles in DCPD monomer with a broadband visible light source. Grubbs catalyst was not included in these suspensions, in order to isolate photothermal heating from heating due to exothermic polymerization. Thermocouples were used to monitor the suspension temperature. We observed an increase in the maximum temperature with both light intensity and nanoparticle loading up to 1 wt%. The addition of 1 wt% CB resulted in approximately a tenfold increase in the temperature rise compared to neat DCPD under the same light intensity.

Photo-activated FROMP experiments were performed using the same experimental setup. For these experiments, Grubbs catalyst was included, along with an equimolar concentration of tributyl

phosphite inhibitor. The time to activation was measured, and the exposure dose required for activation was calculated from the following equation:

$$D = I \times t_{activation} \quad (1)$$

where D = exposure dose (J/cm^2), I = light intensity (W/cm^2), and $t_{activation}$ = time to activation (s).

After activation, the light source was removed, and the front continued to propagate. The addition of 1 wt% CB or 1 wt% CNF reduced the exposure dose required for activation by about 40× compared to neat DCPD resin. The exposure dose is directly proportional to energy consumption for photo-activated FROMP since there is no input of heat.

Nanocomposites prepared by photothermally activated FROMP exhibited similar thermomechanical performance to neat pDCPD including high glass transition temperature and fracture toughness. The changes in the optical properties of the nanocomposites with increasing nanoparticle loading are shown in Figure 4. To the best of our knowledge, this study is the first to utilize light to activate FROMP. This approach should be generally applicable across all FP systems that rely on thermal propagation, since the mechanism of activation is physical rather than chemical.

Figure 4. pDCPD nanocomposites with increasing CB loading from left to right (0, 0.01, 1 wt%).

3 CONDUCTIVE NANOCOMPOSITES MANUFACTURED VIA SIMULTANEOUS 3D PRINTING AND FRONTAL POLYMERIZATION

The nanocomposites described above contained low loadings of carbon nanoparticles (1 wt% or less). In this section, we describe nanocomposites with much higher loadings of carbon nanoparticles (up to 15 wt%). This increase in nanoparticle loading engenders a change in the rheological behavior of the resin to enable direct write 3D printing. Neat DCPD resin is a Newtonian liquid with a low viscosity. At sufficiently high nanoparticle loadings, transient percolated nanoparticle networks form through attractive interactions. This results in yield stress behavior, which is ideal for inks used in direct write 3D printing. Above the yield stress, the ink flows, allowing extrusion through a nozzle. Below the yield stress, the ink resists flow, allowing the ink to maintain its shape after extrusion. The yield stress can be tuned by varying the nanoparticle loading.

DCPD-based inks filled with high loadings of CB were able to maintain their shape upon extrusion and simultaneously undergo FROMP to form nanocomposite structures of arbitrary shape (Figure 5a, b). These nanocomposite structures were conductive enough to power an LED in a simple circuit, unlike neat pDCPD structures. The electrical conductivity of CB nanocomposite films was measured using the 4-point probe technique, and it was found that nanocomposites with 15 wt% CB exhibit electrical conductivity above 10 S/m, which is 18 orders of magnitude greater than neat pDCPD [22]. These experiments demonstrate the potential for rapid manufacturing of multifunctional nanocomposites via simultaneous 3D printing and frontal polymerization.

Figure 5. (a) and (b) Conductive nanocomposites with 15 wt% CB manufactured via simultaneous 3D printing and frontal polymerization. (c) These nanocomposites exhibit sufficient electrical conductivity to power an LED in a simple circuit.

9 CONCLUSIONS

We have demonstrated the manufacturing of nanocomposites via FROMP. These nanocomposites were composed of pDCPD matrix and carbon nanoparticle fillers. Nanocomposites with low nanoparticle loadings (1 wt% or less) were manufactured via photo-activated FROMP. The photothermal effect of the carbon nanoparticles resulted in a dramatic increase in the efficiency of photo-activation. The exposure dose required for photo-activation of DCPD resins containing 1 wt% CB or 1 wt% CNF was 40× less than neat DCPD resin. Nanocomposites with high nanoparticle loadings (up to 15 wt%) were manufactured via simultaneous 3D printing and FROMP. These nanocomposites exhibited electrical conductivity more than 18 orders of magnitude larger than neat pDCPD. Attractive interactions between the nanoparticles imparted yield stress behavior to the resin, enabling extrusion-based processing such as 3D printing. Further work will be done to characterize the mechanical properties of the nanocomposites and to assess their potential as multifunctional materials for sensing applications.

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REFERENCES

- [1] I. D. Robertson *et al.*, “Rapid energy-efficient manufacturing of polymers and composites via frontal polymerization,” *Nature*, vol. 557, no. 7704, pp. 223–227, May 2018.
- [2] N. M. Chechilo, R. J. Khvilivitskii, and N. S. Enikolopyan, “Propagation of the Polymerization Reaction,” *Dokl. Akad. Nauk SSSR*, vol. 204, pp. 1180–1181, 1972.
- [3] J. A. Pojman, “Traveling Fronts of Methacrylic Acid Polymerization,” *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, vol. 113, no. 16, pp. 6284–6286, 1991.
- [4] I. D. Robertson, H. L. Hernandez, S. R. White, and J. S. Moore, “Rapid Stiffening of a Microfluidic Endoskeleton via Frontal Polymerization,” *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, vol. 6, no. 21, pp. 18469–18474, Nov. 2014.
- [5] J. A. Pojman, B. Varisli, A. Perryman, C. Edwards, and C. Hoyle, “Frontal polymerization with

- thiol-ene systems,” *Macromolecules*, vol. 37, no. 3, pp. 691–693, 2004.
- [6] Y. Chekanov, D. Arrington, G. Brust, and J. A. Pojman, “Frontal curing of epoxy resins: Comparison of mechanical and thermal properties to batch-cured materials,” *J. Appl. Polym. Sci.*, vol. 66, no. 6, pp. 1209–1216, 1997.
- [7] C. Kim, H. Teng, C. L. Tucker, and S. R. White, “The Continuous Curing Process for Thermoset Polymer Composites. Part 1: Modeling and Demonstration,” *J. Compos. Mater.*, vol. 29, no. 9, pp. 1222–1253, Jun. 1995.
- [8] A. Mariani, S. Fiori, Y. Chekanov, and J. A. Pojman, “Frontal Ring-Opening Metathesis Polymerization of Dicyclopentadiene,” *Macromolecules*, vol. 34, no. 19, pp. 6539–6541, 2001.
- [9] A. Ruiu, D. Sanna, V. Alzari, D. Nuvoli, and A. Mariani, “Advances in the frontal ring opening metathesis polymerization of dicyclopentadiene,” *J. Polym. Sci. Part A Polym. Chem.*, vol. 52, no. 19, pp. 2776–2780, Oct. 2014.
- [10] I. D. Robertson, E. L. Pruitt, and J. S. Moore, “Frontal Ring-Opening Metathesis Polymerization of Exo-Dicyclopentadiene for Low Catalyst Loadings,” *ACS Macro Lett.*, vol. 5, no. 5, pp. 593–596, May 2016.
- [11] I. D. Robertson, L. M. Dean, G. E. Rudebusch, N. R. Sottos, S. R. White, and J. S. Moore, “Alkyl Phosphite Inhibitors for Frontal Ring-Opening Metathesis Polymerization Greatly Increase Pot Life,” *ACS Macro Lett.*, pp. 609–612, 2017.
- [12] E. Goli, I. D. Robertson, P. H. Geubelle, and J. S. Moore, “Frontal Polymerization of Dicyclopentadiene: A Numerical Study,” *J. Phys. Chem. B*, vol. 122, no. 16, pp. 4583–4591, Apr. 2018.
- [13] S. Barrau, P. Demont, A. Peigney, C. Laurent, and C. Lacabanne, “DC and AC Conductivity of Carbon Nanotubes–Polyepoxy Composites,” *Macromolecules*, vol. 36, no. 14, pp. 5187–5194, Jul. 2003.
- [14] R. Haggemueller, C. Guthy, J. R. Lukes, J. E. Fischer, and K. I. Winey, “Single Wall Carbon Nanotube/Polyethylene Nanocomposites: Thermal and Electrical Conductivity,” *Macromolecules*, vol. 40, no. 7, pp. 2417–2421, Apr. 2007.
- [15] N. Hu, Z. Masuda, C. Yan, G. Yamamoto, H. Fukunaga, and T. Hashida, “The electrical properties of polymer nanocomposites with carbon nanotube fillers,” *Nanotechnology*, vol. 19, no. 21, p. 215701, May 2008.
- [16] R. F. Gibson, “A review of recent research on mechanics of multifunctional composite materials and structures,” *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 92, no. 12, pp. 2793–2810, 2010.
- [17] V. Alzari *et al.*, “Graphene-containing thermoresponsive nanocomposite hydrogels of poly(N-isopropylacrylamide) prepared by frontal polymerization,” *J. Mater. Chem.*, vol. 21, no. 24, pp. 8727–8733, 2011.
- [18] S. Chen, J. Sui, L. Chen, and J. A. Pojman, “Polyurethane-nanosilica hybrid nanocomposites synthesized by frontal polymerization,” *J. Polym. Sci. Part A Polym. Chem.*, vol. 43, no. 8, pp. 1670–1680, 2005.
- [19] A. Mariani, S. Bidali, G. Caria, O. Monticelli, S. Russo, and J. M. Kenny, “Synthesis and characterization of epoxy resin-montmorillonite nanocomposites obtained by frontal polymerization,” *J. Polym. Sci. Part A Polym. Chem.*, vol. 45, no. 11, pp. 2204–2211, Jun. 2007.
- [20] J. D. Mota-Morales *et al.*, “Synthesis of macroporous poly(acrylic acid)-carbon nanotube composites by frontal polymerization in deep-eutectic solvents,” *J. Mater. Chem. A*, vol. 1, no. 12, pp. 3970–3976, 2013.
- [21] R. C. Steinhardt, T. M. Steeves, B. M. Wallace, B. Moser, D. A. Fishman, and A. P. Esser-Kahn, “Photothermal Nanoparticle Initiation Enables Radical Polymerization and Yields Unique, Uniform Microfibers with Broad Spectrum Light,” *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, vol. 9, no. 44, pp. 39034–39039, Nov. 2017.
- [22] K. Yoshida, M. Kozako, S. Ishibe, M. Hikita, and N. Kamei, “Evaluation on Applicability to Electrical Insulating Material of Hydrocarbon-Based Thermosetting Resin,” *Electron. Commun. Japan*, vol. 100, no. 4, pp. 83–90, Apr. 2017.